

Measuring the Effects of Coffee Price Changes on Agricultural Employment in Latin America

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Abstract

Coffee price volatility is often blamed for labour instability in rural Latin America, yet region-wide causal evidence remains sparse. This study collates an unbalanced annual panel for 1997-2022 covering Bolivia, Brazil, Colombia, Costa Rica, Dominican Republic, Ecuador, El Salvador, Mexico, Panama and Peru. Country-specific green coffee farm-gate(producer/farmer) prices from FAOSTAT¹ are merged with employment, macroeconomic and climate indicators. The preferred specification is a fixed effects model with Driscoll-Kraay standard errors, controlling for GDP-per-capita growth, sectoral value-added, exchange rates, oil prices, drought severity, urbanisation, credit depth and migration.

Baseline estimates show a statistically insignificant relationship between my key variables, agricultural employment and change in logged-farmer coffee prices. This implies that mechanisation and long-run structural change have muted the historical price-labour link. Decomposing positive and negative price shocks for my secondary hypothesis yields no evidence of coffee price shock asymmetry. However, augmenting one year farmer price lags makes my model statistically significant at the 1% level: a 1% increase in coffee price results in a 0.01 percentage-point increase in agricultural employment, while the lag term remains insignificant, highlighting that nearly all labour adjustments occur within the season in which the shock is realised.

Several policy implications emerge. First, counter-cyclical support such as price-contingent cash transfers must be triggered swiftly, ideally before the main harvest, to influence agricultural employment. Second, given the modest effect size and the trend toward mechanisation on farms, governments should prioritise productivity-enhancing measures and rural upskilling rather than attempting to stabilise employment numbers.

By providing the first multi-country, post-liberalisation semi-elasticity estimates for Latin America, the study contributes to the literature by providing an empirical basis for coffee policy, highlighting the measurable capacity of price movements to shape rural labour markets.

¹ FAOSTAT represents the Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations Statistical Database

1. Introduction

Coffee has been a prominent export of Latin America since the mid-nineteenth century. The region delivers around 60% of global coffee production, supporting over 25 million rural livelihoods and contributing significantly to export revenues (International Coffee Organisation 2024). Coffee prices are highly volatile, owing to supply, exchange-rate and speculative shocks. There were two key periods of coffee price volatility: The Coffee Crisis in the early 2000s, and the 2010-12 arabica boom. This volatility invites a fundamental question: Do changes in coffee prices feed through to labour demand in agriculture?

1.1 Background

Understanding the dynamics of employment from coffee price swings is central to several policy debates. Coffee is the main crop in many high-altitude regions of Latin American countries such as Brazil. Positive price movements can increase rural incomes and prevent out-migration, whereas negative shocks may cause credit distress or increase child labour. Quantifying the response of agricultural employment to price changes helps governments target temporary income support when world prices drop. Agriculture employment in Brazil fell from 15.8% in 1997 to 8.73% in 2022 (World Bank 2025), showcasing a structural transformation of the economy. Yet the speed and size of this decline differ widely across other Latin American countries. If coffee booms slow the reallocation of labour to urban sectors or if the mechanisation of farming de-links coffee price and employment, development policies may require different complementary policies (training, rural infrastructure and credit). The International Coffee Agreement was disbanded in 1989, exposing growers to market risk but also increasing price transparency and incentives to invest in quality. Estimating labour effects since liberalisation provides evidence on whether agricultural employment volatility has dampened, informing ongoing discussions about producer country buffer stocks, minimum price interventions and exchange rate management.

1.2 Existing Evidence and Gaps

Empirical work confirms that coffee prices can shift employment, however, many studies were done at a micro-level. For example, micro-panel studies from Vietnam (Beck, Singhal & Tarp 2018) and Tanzania (Adhvaryu et al. 2021) reveal intra-household reallocations toward other sectors and small enterprises when prices fall. Simulation models for Brazil in the 1970s (Adams et al. 1979) suggest potentially large macro impacts, yet they rely on dated parameters. No paper estimates the empirical response between producer-price changes and country-level agricultural employment for Latin America during the modern, post-liberalisation era (1997-2022). Moreover, the dynamic profile and potential asymmetry of the relationship, do busts affect agricultural employment more than booms, remain unexplored.

1.3 Research Hypotheses

The first hypothesis is derived from theoretical intuition (discussed in Section 2.1). The second hypothesis is derived from Ghoshray & Mohan (2021), who find asymmetry of the impact of positive and negative price shocks.

H₁: Positive price changes increase agricultural employment

H₂: The response between coffee price and agriculture employment is larger in absolute value for negative price shocks than for positive shocks

1.4 Preview of Data, Empirical Strategy and Study Structure

To test these hypotheses, I have collated an unbalanced panel of ten major Latin American coffee exporters (Brazil, Colombia, Peru, Bolivia, Mexico, Panama, Costa Rica, Dominican Republic, El Salvador and Ecuador) for the study period 1997-2022. Farm-gate prices come from FAOSTAT. Agricultural employment and macro controls are sourced from the World Bank World Development Indicators. The climate shock is sourced from the SPEI drought monitor, and oil prices from the World Bank Commodity Price Pink Sheets.

The regression encompasses agricultural employment share being regressed on log farm-gate price changes, GDP-per capita growth, sectoral value-added shares, urban population, private credit depth, exchange rates, oil prices, net migration and drought levels. Country and year fixed effects absorb unobserved heterogeneity and global shocks. Driscoll-Kraay standard errors are used to account for autocorrelation, heteroskedasticity and cross-sectional dependence.

The remainder of the dissertation proceeds as follows. Section 2 analyses the theoretical and empirical literature. Section 3 presents the data, Section 4 showcases methodology, Section 5 discusses results, and Section 6 concludes.

2. Literature Review

This literature review will analyse studies which are conducted at both macro and micro levels, helping to gain a deeper insight into how the coffee market affects labour dynamics. Historical and descriptive studies are also included, as they provide context to certain regression results. Many of the studies also guide me on what control measures to augment into my model specification. The following literature review is organised with an initial theoretical section and four different themes: Macro-level Employment and Output Responses, Price Formation and Pass-through to producers, Micro-level Labour Allocation Responses, Structural and Historical Factors.

2.1 Theoretical Underpinnings: Why Coffee Prices Matter For Agricultural Employment

Coffee is a significant traded crop and a cornerstone of rural labour markets in Latin America, which supplies roughly 60% of the coffee globally (International Coffee Organisation 2024). This suggests that coffee plays an important role for

agricultural workers in the region. High coffee prices can cause farmers to expand their labour supply as they want to maximise output and capitalise on high prices, leading to higher agricultural employment. This is my theoretical foundation for my primary hypothesis. My secondary hypothesis is grounded in the works of Ghoshray & Mohan (2021), who find asymmetry in the transmission mechanisms of coffee price changes.

2.2 Macro-Level Employment and Output Responses

Early simulation models for Brazil (Adams et al. 1979) embedded a ‘coffee block’ in a macroeconomic framework. They run a counterfactual in which Brazilian coffee yields are held above 10% baseline for 1976-87 and compare two scenarios: (i) the extra beans are stockpiled domestically, (ii) they are exported at an unchanged world price. GDP increases by 0.44% in (i) and 0.82% in (ii), while coffee-sector employment rises between 3.7% and 4.7% and non-farm employment by roughly 4% through Keynesian multiplier effects. However, three-quarters of the aggregate income gain comes from induced spending on services and capital goods rather than the farm sector itself. Two critical points reduce the usefulness of these elasticities for my multi-country, post-1997 study. First, Brazil’s ability to divert 17% more coffee onto world markets without moving the world price is implausible given its one-third share of global output. Secondly, the model imposes no capacity constraints outside agriculture, thus, the estimated 4% spillover effect is likely overstated. Still, the paper convincingly maps the export tax and balance of payments channels through which coffee shocks expand, reinforcing my decision to control for GDP-per-capita growth and exchange rate effects. Modern identification derives from structural VARs. Bodenstein, Kamber & Thoenissen (2018) construct a quarterly panel-VAR for Australia, Canada and New Zealand (from quarter 3 1994 to quarter 4 2013). The authors find that a one standard deviation rise in the commodity-price index triggers a 10 basis-point fall in the unemployment rate and a 3% rise in job vacancies within three quarters. Real exchange rates appreciate by 0.8%, reallocating labour toward non-tradable jobs. These findings highlight that fluctuations in commodities can alter labour market dynamics within countries. However, extrapolating these responses to Latin America risks upward bias. Firstly, Latin America likely has greater labour market frictions, meaning the shift toward non-tradable jobs is weaker. Secondly, the authors’ model implies a rapidly changing exchange rate, although several Latin American economies (such as Brazil and Colombia) operate a managed exchange rate policy and face binding foreign-exchange reserve constraints, reducing the wealth effect. Implications of these differences include smaller and slower employment boosts per dollar of coffee-price increase.

2.3 Price Formation and Pass-through to Producers

Global Fundamentals

A VECM by Aliaga-Lordemann et al. (2021) finds that Arabica prices cointegrate with oil, stock-to-use ratios and the BRL/USD² rate.

Oil prices are included as a proxy for global shipping and freight costs. Changes in oil prices can directly raise the cost of transporting coffee beans as fuel for ships is more expensive, impacting various points in the coffee supply chain from green bean transportation to delivering roasted beans to end-markets. Stock-to-use ratios are a typical measure of the level of supply of a commodity. It is defined as an end-of-season carryover divided by total annual consumption. A higher ratio signals ample inventories relative to demand, causing downward pressure on prices and vice versa. The BRL/USD real exchange rate is used as Brazil accounts for roughly one-third of global Arabica coffee output. Fluctuations in exchange rates affect Brazilian farmers' BRL-denominated revenue. A weaker BRL will result in Brazilian coffee being cheaper for international buyers, resulting in decreased pressure on the dollar price of Arabica. These findings guide me to include oil prices and exchange rates in my model specification, I could not implement coffee inventories as I could not find sufficient data.

Price Transmission Asymmetry

Ghoshray & Mohan (2021) find strong evidence of price transmission asymmetry in the coffee supply chain using a momentum-TAR model, highlighting that negative international price shocks pass through to US retail prices 70% faster than positive shocks. This suggests that roasters with more market power absorb gains during price booms as profit but pass losses down the supply chain during price slumps. However, evidence from other settings is mixed; studies in Europe often find more symmetric pass-through, especially where retail competition is higher, as noted by the authors. These findings motivate decomposing log price changes into positive and negative components in my analysis to test the secondary hypothesis. If downward shocks reduce agricultural employment more sharply than upward shocks raise it, this will confirm that market power along the value chain dampens the benefits of price booms for coffee farmers while magnifying the harms of busts.

Pass-through Magnitudes

Micro-evidence from Tanzania (Adhvaryu et al. 2021) suggests that farm-gate level coffee prices are a good proxy for country-specific coffee prices. Their empirical model for testing this involved:

$$P_{it}^{farm} = \pi + \theta \ln P_t^W + \mu_i + \delta_t + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (1)$$

P_{it}^{farm} – Farm-gate price (in real Tanzanian Shilling/kg)

π – Constant Term

² BRL/USD stands for the exchange rate value between the Brazilian Real and the US Dollar

μ – Household Fixed-effects

δ_t - Wave Dummies

ε – Residual Term

i and t represent farmer and wave respectively

Using 3 waves of a national Tanzanian survey (2004-12), they find the coefficient of world price θ to be between 0.7-0.9, with strong statistical significance at the 1% level. This finding is imperative for my study, which utilises farm-gate coffee prices as a measure of country-specific coffee prices. However, caution should be exercised when using this finding for my study in Latin America. This is because of the policy environment, during the Tanzania study period, the country abolished its Coffee Marketing Board export tax, a reform which may have elevated the coefficient. Several Latin American countries still levy export registration fees or quality levies that can dampen transmission.

2.4 Micro-level Labour-allocation Responses

Economic theory predicts that a coffee price shock can change the shadow wage on coffee farms, potentially reallocating labour within the household (including child labour) and affecting child schooling.

Beck, Singhal & Tarp (2018) exploit four rounds (2006-12) of a Vietnamese national survey and monthly robusta price data. The authors employ a 12-month lag Robusta coffee price measure to ensure the price variable is predetermined with respect to the survey reference period and cannot be influenced by the household's current-year labour decisions. I will employ a similar one-year lagged model in Section 5.4. Using rainfall-driven coffee yield deviations as an instrument, they estimate a 35% fall in world Robusta price increases adult off-farm work by 6%, while child labour jumps by 17%. Heterogeneity tests reveal that the substitution effect is stronger for women, certain ethnic groups and households with poor credit access. This finding suggests that true employment response measures may be misleading, as child labour is not reported in national employment figures. Specifically, hours worked on a farm may not be reduced despite a negative agricultural employment response, as children are substituted in place of adults, likely due to cheaper labour costs. However, labour mobility in Vietnam is low, due to the Ho Khau system³, meaning adults may be 'pushed' into local wage jobs. In contrast, Latin America faced mass migration across the region due to the early 2000s coffee crisis, as reported by Varangis et al (2003), therefore, children may not substitute adults as adults seek income equivalent work in urban areas.

In Tanzania, falling prices incentivise coffee farmers to start-up low low-capital micro enterprises, particularly in asset-poor households (Adhvaryu et al.

³ The Ho Khau System was a household registration system in Vietnam that inhibited internal migration by requiring government approval for changes in residence, this policy limited rural-urban migration during the study period.

2021). The behavioural response to price changes implies that asset holdings determine adjustment margins. Latin American evidence is lacking, but I proxy this mechanism by including private-sector credit in the model.

Varangis et al (2003) provide descriptive evidence on the social consequences of the Coffee Crisis between 2000-2002. During this period, international Arabica coffee prices fell below production costs, leading to widespread income losses and a drastic fall in coffee sector employment (permanent employment fell by over 50%, and seasonal jobs fell by more than 20%). This report emphasises that regions highly dependent on coffee, for example Nicaragua, where 42% of rural labour was tied to coffee, faced migration pressures, increases in child labour and school dropout rates. However, the descriptive nature of the report limits causal interpretation, as there is no econometric identification strategy to isolate the impact of coffee prices from other confounding factors like droughts or economic shocks. Despite this, this paper motivates the inclusion of migration as a control in my study.

On the other hand, Bussolo et al. (2006) evaluate the effects of a coffee price boom in Uganda following market liberalisation, using household data between 1992-2000. They find a strong correlation between coffee price rises and poverty reduction, especially for poorer farmers who increased their investment in both agriculture and non-agricultural activities. The authors also note that multiplier effects were concentrated in coffee-growing regions, amplifying welfare gains. This study provides some empirical evidence for the theoretical foundations of this study. Increased investment after coffee price hikes may incentivise expanding farms, increasing demand for workers and thus increasing agricultural employment. However, the authors acknowledge limitations, including the lack of panel data use, which reduces the ability to track dynamic household-level adjustments. Moreover, although Uganda offers a valuable contrast to Latin America, it differs structurally from many Latin American countries in terms of landholding systems, access to credit and policy environments, raising concerns about external validity.

2.5 Structural and Historical Factors

Coffee labour markets at present have been shaped by deep institutional and ecological legacies.

Roseberry (1991) documents entrenched historical systems that still have an effect today in Latin America. The author reports oligarchic landownership structures and quasi-feudal labour systems that created long-term constraints on rural labour mobility and the ability for workers to bargain wages. These institutions had a large influence going forward into the 20th century, and their legacy persists to this day through the prevalence of informal hiring and limited upward mobility for seasonal coffee workers. These entrenched structures help to explain why the labour market may be unresponsive to coffee price changes.

Bacsi et al (2022) highlight how yield-instability, driven by factors such as climate shocks, not only destabilises household incomes but also worsens national food security in coffee-dependent economies. The authors apply a Yield Stability Index (YSI) to identify long-run fluctuations in coffee output, showing that volatility is especially high in smallholder farms with weak irrigation systems and poor access to stabilising technologies. Applying their YSI, they find that Nicaragua's Arabica yield volatility doubled between 1995-2019, leading to both tightening credit access and labour demand. I have included drought shocks in my model specification to capture climate-driven volatility.

Recent evidence suggests that farmers have faced severe leaf-rust epidemics around 2012-2014, wiping out large amounts of coffee production and increasing farming costs across Latin America (Harvey et al. 2021). The authors report that a large 'reconfiguration' of farmland is taking place. This 'reconfiguration' involves several key parts, including mechanisation to intensify production and increase output, switching to alternative sectors and in some exceptional cases, farmland may be sold to be converted into urban development. All these mechanisms can help to explain labour market dynamics. This study has also given me the intuition to augment urban population and the value-added of alternative sectors in the economy as control measures in the model.

2.6 Literature Summary

Commodity-price studies portray that commodity price swings can affect labour market dynamics, although evidence of coffee price swings specifically is lacking; studies are often pre-1990, single-country or at the household-level, with little coverage of Latin America's liberalised era. Papers do not test whether busts shrink employment more than booms expand it. Many also do not examine how employment adjusts over several years after a coffee price change while controlling for climate, migration and macro shocks. My research fills these gaps by compiling a 1997-2022 panel for ten major Latin American exporters, measuring the changes in agricultural employment in response to farmer price changes. I will employ a similar lagged methodology to Beck, Singhal & Tarp (2018).

3. Data

3.1 Data Selection

This panel study analyses the relationship between coffee price changes and agricultural employment in Latin American countries between the periods 1997-2022. This study period provides a clear, 26-year panel that begins just after the post-International Coffee Agreement price liberalisation shock, runs through the 2000s commodity boom-bust cycles, major policy and climate shocks in Latin America, ending with the COVID-19 recovery period. This period provides both historical breadth and up-to-date relevance. Recent years 2023 and 2024 could not

be used as the datasets for the key variables are not complete. Table 1 shows 16 countries within Latin America that fit the criterion of producing at least 100,000 60kg coffee bags on average in 2022 (Foreign Agricultural Service 2022). 10 out of 16 countries from Table 1 are selected due to data coverage. Excluded countries are highlighted in grey. The production selection criteria were created to ensure countries with a substantial modern-day coffee market are selected for study.

Table 1: Mean Production of Coffee (Green) in 2022 (Measured in 1000 60kg bags)

Country	Mean Production
Brazil	49650
Colombia	11643
Honduras	4404
Mexico	4108
Guatemala	3815
Peru	3514
Nicaragua	1954
Costa Rica	1719
El Salvador	1153
Venezuela	749
Ecuador	599
Dominican Republic	352
Haiti	231
Cuba	160
Bolivia	120
Panama	117

3.2 Key Variables

The key explanatory variable is the annual change in logged farm-gate prices of green coffee. Farm-gate price is used as a proxy for country-specific coffee prices and is defined as the price at which green coffee leaves the farm, excluding any costs beyond the farm-gate level (e.g transport to market). Green coffee is defined as coffee beans before any processing. The dependent variable is agricultural employment, measured as a percentage of total employment in a country. Agriculture employment is sourced from the World Development Indicators (WDI) from the World Bank. Farm-gate prices are sourced from the FAOSTAT database.

3.3 Control Variables

The choice of control measures has been guided by the literature to minimise heterogeneity within the model. Adams et al (1979) simulation model approach gives reason to include GDP-per capita growth as a control. World oil prices and exchange rates have been guided by Aliaga Lordemann et al (2021), Bacsi et al (2022) have guided the drought-measure (SPEI-Index), Harvey et al (2021) have guided urban population levels and sectoral value-added measures. Advaryu et al (2021) guided private sector credit accessibility. Finally, Varangis et al (2002) findings give us evidence to implement net migration as a control. All controls have been sourced from reliable international organisations, which the literature has also utilised throughout. Please find data sources in the reference list. All controls are annual measures.

Table 2: Control Variables List, Definitions and Sources

Variable	Definition	Data Source
Agriculture, forestry and fishing value added (% of GDP)	Includes crop and livestock production, forestry, hunting and fishing. Value added is calculated as output minus intermediate inputs, excluding depreciation and resource depletion (ISIC ⁴ Divisions 1-3)	WDI (2025)
GDP per capita annual % growth	Annual % change in economic output per person, measured in constant local currency	WDI (2025)
Manufacturing, Value Added (% of GDP)	Net output of manufacturing industries after subtracting intermediate inputs from output (ISIC Divisions 15-37)	WDI (2025)

⁴ ISIC stands for International Standard Industrial Classification of All Economic Activities, developed by United Nations

Net Migration (x10000)	The number of immigrants minus the number of emigrants, including both citizens and non-citizens, scaled down by 10000	WDI (2025)
Oil Price (\$ per barrel)	Crude Oil Price, average 12-month spot price of Brent, Dubai and West Texas Intermediate, equal weightage	World Bank Commodity Price Data (Pink Sheet) (2024)
Private Sector Credit (% of GDP)	Domestic credit given to the private sector through instruments such as loans	WDI (2025)
Δ Log-Official Exchange Rate (LCU ⁵ per US\$)	12-month average exchange rate determined by national authorities, annual change in logged form	WDI (2025)
SPEI ⁶ Index (drought measure)	Captures the balance between precipitation and evapotranspiration; positive values indicate wet conditions and vice versa, 12-month average	Global SPEI Database (2010)
Services, Value Added (% of GDP)	Net output of service-related industries (ISIC Divisions 50-99), calculated as total output minus intermediate inputs	WDI (2025)
Urban Population (% of total population)	Number of people living in urban areas as defined by national statistical offices in each country	WDI (2025)

3.4 Data Cleaning and Processing

Many of my variables were derived from the World Bank's WDI database, which meant not many datasets had to be merged. The variables that had to be merged with the WDI indicators were farmer prices, oil price and the SPEI index numbers. All datasets were transformed into a long format to ensure consistency in merging, and variable names were made consistent. Several redundant columns were dropped, formulating a clear panel dataset with model variables. The SPEI database proved to be a challenging database to navigate, as the dataset had a tremendous amount of datapoints (approximately 30 million), hence, specialist software had to be utilised to derive the relevant data. I have taken the logarithms of the farmer

⁵ LCU stands for Local Currency Units

⁶ SPEI stands for Standardised Precipitation-Evapotranspiration Index

price and exchange rate variables. I have also scaled down the net migration variable by 10,000 to improve interpretability.

3.5 Summary Statistics

Table 3: Summary Statistics of Key Variables and Controls

	Mean	Standard Deviation	Min	Max
Agricultural Employment (% of total employment)	20.25	8.23	7.71	44.2
$\Delta \text{Log}(\text{Farmer Price})$.02	.34	-1.51	3.15
$\Delta \text{Log}(\text{Exchange Rate LCU/USD})$	-.014	.618	-9.37	.77
GDP Per Capita Growth (%)	2.3	3.83	-18.94	15.07
Agriculture, Forestry & Fishing (% of GDP)	6.83	2.95	2.45	20.11
Urban Population (% of Total)	71.63	8.06	56.37	87.56
Manufacturing (% of GDP)	14.3	3.82	5.09	23.94
Private Sector Credit (% of GDP)	41.2	19.85	11.04	104.62
Net Migration ($\times 10\,000$)	-4.76	11	-37.98	49.55
Services (% of GDP)	57.54	6.71	40.21	73.96
SPEI	-.15	.93	-2.73	3.49
Oil Price (\$/barrel)	58.73	24.23	15.9	95.26
Observations	260			

Table 3 showcases summary statistics. Notable insights include the maximum value of agricultural employment being 44.2% (Bolivia 2001), with the mean being around 20.3%. This shows us that the agricultural sector is significant to some economies in the sample, employing a large proportion of the nation's workforce. The change log farmer price variable has a modest mean; farm-gate prices of coffee increased on average by 2% throughout the study period, however, the standard deviation is 34%, indicating great volatility. Some notable summary statistics of the controls include GDP-per capita growth having a max value of 15.1% (Panama 2021) and a minimum of -18.94% (Panama 2020), Panama experienced an extremely volatile economic cycle within a year, likely driven by the COVID-19 pandemic. We also observe extreme exchange rate volatility, with the standard deviation being 62% in the sample, which can imply that coffee farmers likely faced great economic uncertainty as farm revenue varied because of the exchange rate.

3.6 Bivariate Relationship

Figure 1: Bivariate relationship between agricultural employment and change in log farmer prices

Figure 1 portrays a simple bivariate relationship between key variables. I have decided to showcase this relationship in Brazil, as Brazil is a significant Arabica coffee producer (Aliaga-Lordemann et al. 2021). We can see the agriculture employment share declining rapidly between the years 2005 and 2011, likely because of economic development and shifting economic activity to other sectors. Despite this, post-employment share decline, agricultural employment appears to track changes in farmer price, with a slight delay. This provided us with the intuition to test lags within my model specification in Section 5.4. We also observe farmer prices plummeting due to the early 2000s coffee price crisis, and the coffee price boom, which raised farmer prices between 2010-2011. Neither of the global coffee price shocks seem to affect Brazil's agriculture employment share significantly, however, this is only a visual correlation, and many macroeconomic and structural forces likely confound the relationship. Formal estimation is needed to isolate the effect of coffee price changes on employment outcomes. Similar coffee price volatility and two-way relationships were observed for the other 9 countries in the sample.

3.7 Data Limitations

A key data issue involves the change in the log-farmer price variable. The first study year (1997) observations are omitted as I take annual log differences (this is the same case for the log exchange rate variable), resulting in 10 observations being dropped. In addition, there are missing data points, resulting in an unbalanced panel. These data points are missing for unknown reasons in random years (for example, Costa Rica 2019-2022). These missing points are in consecutive gaps, with the longest gap being 3 years, as shown. I utilise Stata software, which performs case-wise deletion, so any observation missing one of the variables in a model specification is automatically dropped. This makes the usable sample in the baseline specifications drop from 260 to 226 (approximately 13% fewer observations). All regression output tables in Section 5 report the actual number of country-years retained (N) for transparency. The implications of these issues include lower statistical power of my model through wider standard errors and a greater chance of type II error. Missingness is random, therefore, sample-selection bias is not present.

Beyond the issue of missing observations, the quality and consistency of underlying data sources can present limitations, despite data being sourced from reputable sources. Agricultural employment may suffer from cross-country inconsistencies due to variation in how employment status is measured and defined, for example, if armed forces personnel are counted, in addition to the usage of establishment surveys, which exclude workers in the informal economy. Moreover, variation in the age groups covered, treatment of unemployed individuals and use of different ISIC classifications (Revisions 2, 3 or 4) reduce comparability of employment numbers across countries and over time. As a result, agricultural employment responses should be interpreted with caution, as changes may not reflect real labour market dynamics. Limitations of farm-gate coffee price data arise from how countries define, collect and report producer prices. Although prices are attempted to be recorded at the point of initial sale, some countries substitute these with wholesale, local market or retail prices, depending on the availability of national data. This can introduce measurement error, especially in countries with longer and more fragmented supply chains. Geographic and temporal comparability is also affected by inconsistent coverage, reporting frequency and changes in national statistical offices. These limitations carry over to some controls, e.g private sector credit, introducing measurement error.

4. Methodology

4.1 Model Specifications

I test the primary hypothesis through the following fixed effects panel regression model with both country-specific and time fixed effects:

$$AgEmp_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta \Delta \text{Log}(\text{FarmerPrice})_{i,t} + \gamma X_{i,t} + \mu_i + \delta_t + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (2)$$

- i and t represent country and year respectively
- α : Constant Term
- β : Coefficient Term
- γX : Vector of controls with respective coefficients
- μ : Country-Fixed Effects
- δ : Year-Fixed Effects
- ε : Error Term

I test the secondary hypothesis of asymmetric effects through the following model:

$$AgEmp_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta^+ \Delta \text{Log}(\text{FarmerPrice})_{i,t}^+ + \beta^- \Delta \text{Log}(\text{FarmerPrice})_{i,t}^- + \gamma X_{i,t} + \mu_i + \delta_t + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (3)$$

Symbology is the same as above, additionally, I define $\Delta \text{Log}(\text{FarmerPrice})_{i,t}^+$ as the change in log farmer price when it is positive (and 0 otherwise) and $\Delta \text{Log}(\text{FarmerPrice})_{i,t}^-$ as the absolute (abs) value of the change when it is negative (and 0 otherwise). After running the secondary regression, I conduct an equality test to test the secondary hypothesis, with the null hypothesis being that both the positive and negative coefficients are the same.

The model utilises both country-specific and time fixed effects. We conduct a Hausman test to validate our fixed-effects model approach. We strongly reject the null hypothesis that states that a random effects model is a better fit, suggesting that there is a systematic difference between the coefficients estimated by the random and fixed effects models, implying that random effects assumptions are violated. In the context of this study, the result implies that country-specific time-invariant factors such as land quality or historical policies are correlated with the explanatory variables. Time-fixed effects are included, after conducting a joint F-test of year dummy variables, the variables were not jointly different from 0, controlling for variables that are constant across countries but vary over time. The fixed effects model is more appropriate as it controls for these unobserved heterogeneities, providing more reliable and unbiased coefficient estimates for the analysis.

4.2 Diagnostic Tests

I run a series of diagnostic tests to check and address heteroskedasticity, autocorrelation and cross-sectional dependence within the model. I detect groupwise heteroskedasticity using the modified Wald's test, which confirms that

error variances differ significantly across economies, possibly because Brazil's coffee sector is far larger and more volatile than Panama's, for example, reducing estimator efficiency. First-order serial correlation is present; this was found after conducting the Woolridge test. This means errors between different years are correlated, which violates the strict exogeneity condition of the error term. Both ordinary and clustered standard errors may shrink or exaggerate statistical significance; test results can also mean the model has not captured dynamic adjustment. After carrying out Pesaran's cross-sectional dependence test, I also detected cross-sectional dependence within the panel. This means that contemporaneous shocks, such as global price swings or regional weather events, are transmitted at the same time to several Latin American countries. When residuals are correlated across countries, variance-covariance matrices that assume independence underestimate sampling variability and inflate t-statistics. All of these issues can result in inference becoming unreliable; to resolve all three issues simultaneously, I regress all models with Driscoll-Kraay standard errors.

4.3 Multicollinearity

Variance-inflation factors (VIF) for the baseline model are reassuring: the mean VIF is 2.66, and all covariates fall well below the conventional actionable threshold of 5, except oil price (10.1). The higher VIF for oil price is expected given its comovement with exchange rates and GDP per capita growth, but it affects only its precision and does not alter the significance of coffee-price coefficients, hence multicollinearity does not bias inferences drawn from output tables in the results section. Oil prices in the literature are flagged as important determinants of coffee prices, hence remain in the model specification.

4.4 Robustness Strategy

For robustness, I implement one-year farmer price lags, following a similar approach to Beck, Singhal & Tarp (2018), who employ one-year lagged coffee prices to assess their impact on household-level labour allocation. I only apply one-year lags to the primary hypothesis regression, the lagged variable is introduced here as a diagnostic exercise. I do not include one-year lags in our baseline specification as I want to preserve degrees of freedom. With just 26 annual observations per country, retaining observations helps keep statistical power. After implementing lags, observations (N) drop from 226 to 212, which will be seen in the output tables in the results section. The model specification is as follows (same symbology as above):

$$AgEmp_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_0 \Delta \text{Log}(\text{FarmerPrice})_{i,t} + \beta_1 \Delta \text{Log}(\text{FarmerPrice})_{i,t-1} + \gamma X_{i,t} + \mu_i + \delta_t + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (4)$$

5. Results

5.1 Baseline Model Results

Table 4a: Model Specification Build-up

	(1) Country Fixed- Effects only	(2) + Year Fixed- Effects	(3) + Macro stabilisers
$\Delta \text{Log}(\text{Farmer Price})$	-1.039	-0.577	-0.363
	(0.821)	(0.381)	(0.649)
$\Delta \text{Log}(\text{Exchange Rate})$			0.165
			(0.269)
GDP per Capita Growth (%)			-0.012
			(0.049)
Constant	20.070*** (0.714)	17.932*** (0.092)	17.376*** (0.465)
R-squared ⁷	0.016	0.586	0.587
Observations	228	228	228

Standard errors in parentheses, Time fixed effects included in models 2–3 (not shown). All models use Driscoll-Kraay standard errors hereafter. ⁸ $p < 0.10$, $** p < 0.05$, $*** p < 0.01$

Table 4b: Model-Specification Build-up Continued

	(4) + Structural controls	(5) + Demographics & Finance	(6) + Oil and Climate Shock
$\Delta \text{Log}(\text{Farmer Price})$	0.215	0.505	0.561
	(0.401)	(0.440)	(0.458)
$\Delta \text{Log}(\text{Exchange Rate})$	0.225*	0.147	0.161
	(0.126)	(0.112)	(0.118)

⁷ All R-Squared statistics are reported as 'Within R-squared'

⁸ * Indicate level of significance, no * indicates no statistical significance

GDP per Capita Growth (%)	-0.035 (0.038)	-0.068* (0.038)	-0.070* (0.037)
Agri-forestry-fishing value (% GDP)	-0.670*** (0.125)	-0.665*** (0.129)	-0.696*** (0.125)
Manufacturing (% GDP)	0.166* (0.087)	0.194* (0.112)	0.191* (0.111)
Services (% GDP)	0.185** (0.071)	0.357*** (0.084)	0.355*** (0.084)
Urban Pop (% of Total)		-0.200** (0.078)	-0.200** (0.078)
Private Credit (% GDP)		-0.072*** (0.023)	-0.071*** (0.024)
Net Migration ($\times 10\ 000$)		-0.032** (0.015)	-0.031** (0.015)
SPEI			0.168 (0.127)
Oil Price			0.194** (0.071)
Constant	0.000 (.)	0.000 (.)	0.000 (.)
R-squared	0.663	0.694	0.696
Observations	228	226	226

Standard errors in parentheses. Time and Country fixed effects included in all models (not shown).

* $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$

Tables 4a and 4b show incremental specifications of the model. I start with country-fixed effects alone in column (1), add year fixed effects (2), macro-stabilisers (3), structural-sector shares (4), demographic & finance controls (5) and finally oil and climate shocks (6). This stepwise build-up shows how the level-log model behaves as potential sources of omitted variables are progressively absorbed. Columns (5) and (6) do not showcase significant differences in coefficient estimates, however, I still decide to use (6) as the fully specified model for the rest of the study. This is because Aliaga Lordemann et al (2021) and Bacsi et al (2022) provide evidence of oil prices and the drought measure, SPEI, as important controls to augment. The coefficient estimate for the key variable change in log farmer price goes from negative in the basic country effects only model (1) to positive in the fully specified model (6), from -1.04 to 0.56. The coefficient estimate would suggest that a 1% rise in coffee-farmer price would increase agriculture employment share by only 0.0056pp⁹, ceteris paribus, although this estimate is not statistically significant at any conventional significance levels, offering no support for H₁. Several factors can explain this, firstly Harvey et al. (2021) document rising mechanical harvesting and capital-intensive pruning, which disassociate labour demand from price swings. Roseberry (1991) emphasises entrenched smallholder structures and shadow labour markets; additional hours worked by family members when prices spike are unlikely to appear in official agricultural employment figures. Additionally, increasing the hours worked of hired workers may be a cheaper alternative to sourcing additional workers, making agricultural employment figures insensitive to changes in coffee price. The progressive model build-up demonstrates that the statistical insignificance is not caused by over or under-controlling. Despite the coefficient sign changing from negative to positive, it never approaches significance. The within-R-squared rises from 0.016 in the country-fixed-effects only model to 0.696 in the full specification, highlighting that the group of controls explain almost 70% of the year-to-year variation within countries.

5.2 Control Variables

We do observe several of the control variables being very statistically significant. All variable interpretations in this subsection have the ceteris paribus assumption. GDP per capita growth is weakly significant at the 10% level; a 1% rise in GDP per capita results in a 0.07pp fall in agricultural employment. This could reflect structural transformation dynamics, as economies grow, more productive and higher wage jobs emerge in non-agriculture sectors, resulting in the agriculture employment share falling. When Agriculture, forestry & fishing value added increases by 1%, agriculture employment falls by 0.7pp. This may be due to more capital-intensive farming in mature farm sectors as the sector gets more developed

⁹ Pp stands for percentage-points

and has a greater share of GDP. As the urban population share increases by 1%, agricultural employment falls by 0.2pp, reflecting rural-urban migration pressures documented by Varangis et al (2003). Private sector credit rising by 1% results in a 0.07pp fall in agricultural employment. As credit markets get deeper, farmers may seek exit from low-productivity agricultural work, shrinking the agricultural workforce. As the manufacturing value added share increases by 1%, agricultural employment increases by 0.19pp. This is unexpected, as theoretical models predict that as manufacturing develops, the economy shifts away from agriculture; this result might indicate that both sectors expand simultaneously during economic booms. This finding is similar for the services value-added share variable; as service sector value-added increases by 1%, agricultural employment increases by 0.4pp. Higher services sector value-added may be associated with larger seasonal farm-labour demand (tourism, logistics). Net migration has the following estimate: a net inflow of 10000 additional people into a country is associated with a 0.03pp decrease in agricultural employment share, which may be due to migrants choosing sectors with the highest expected wage (typically urban-based roles), resulting in lower agricultural employment share. Finally, as oil prices increase by 1\$/barrel, agricultural employment falls by 0.19pp. This is likely due to cost-push effects as a higher fuel price reduces farms' margins, resulting in reduced hiring. The remaining controls (exchange rate changes and drought proxy SPEI) are statistically insignificant, this may be due to fixed effects already capturing much of the macro variation that would otherwise influence agricultural employment.

5.3 Secondary Hypothesis Results

Table 5: Asymmetric Elasticities (Positive vs Negative Shocks)

		(1)
		Agricultural Employment
Δ	Log(Farmer Price) (+)	0.626 (0.911)
Δ	Log(Farmer Price) (-, abs)	-0.506 (0.794)
R-Squared		0.696
N		226

Standard errors in parentheses. Time and Country Fixed Effects included (not shown).

* $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$

To test H₂ I split price changes into positive and negative components. The rest of my model is identical to the baseline specification (6), therefore, I only report

the farmer price coefficients. Neither positive nor negative price shocks are statistically significant (as seen in Table 5), and an equality test (Wald's test) failed to reject the equality of the two slopes. This null result contrasts with Ghoshray & Mohan (2021), who find asymmetric pass-through further down the value chain in the US. The reasoning behind this result may be that mitigating government interventions may blunt job losses during price slumps. Beck, Singhal & Tarp (2018) also highlight Vietnamese coffee farmers reallocating labour within their households, drawing on unpaid family labour during price slumps, making agricultural employment insensitive; this mechanism may also occur on Latin American farms.

5.4 Robustness: Dynamic Model Specification

Table 6: One-year lag farmer price specification

	Agricultural Employment
$\Delta \text{Log}(\text{Farmer Price})$	1.060 ^{***}
	(0.332)
Lagged $\Delta \text{Log}(\text{Farmer Price})$	-0.203
	(0.279)
$\Delta \text{Log}(\text{Exchange Rate})$	0.283 ^{***}
	(0.087)
GDP per Capita Growth (%)	-0.065
	(0.041)
Agri-forestry-fishing (% GDP)	-0.773 ^{***}
	(0.121)
Urban Pop (% of Total)	-0.192 ^{**}
	(0.074)

Manufacturing (% GDP)	0.222*
	(0.123)
Private Credit (% GDP)	-0.078***
	(0.022)
Net Migration ($\times 10\ 000$)	-0.032*
	(0.018)
Services (% GDP)	0.400***
	(0.078)
SPEI	0.252**
	(0.120)
Oil Price	0.164**
	(0.061)
Constant	0.000
	(.)
R-Squared	0.711
N	212

Standard errors in parentheses. Year and Country fixed effects included but not shown.

* $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$

To gauge whether labour reallocation unfolds gradually rather than in a short period, I re-estimate the full model including a one-year lagged change in log-coffee farmer price. The results shown in Table 6 reveal several key findings. Firstly, the current response intensifies: the response of agriculture employment to current-year farmer price changes rises from 0.0056pp to 0.0106pp, consistent with short-run hiring surges when coffee revenues rise. Secondly, the lagged term coefficient is statistically insignificant, indicating that most of the adjustment is completed within the harvest year, and any subsequent correction is small and imprecisely estimated. Most control variables display the same behaviour as the baseline specification; however, changes in log exchange rate and drought-measure

SPEI become statistically significant in the lagged specification. A 1% depreciation in the domestic country against the US dollar is associated with a 0.003pp increase in agricultural employment (*ceteris paribus*). This is likely driven by improved export competitiveness of agricultural commodities, resulting in improved farm revenues, causing farmers to expand and hire more labour. A one-unit increase in SPEI results in a 0.252pp increase in agricultural employment (*ceteris paribus*), which is in line with theoretical expectations; a higher SPEI indicates a wetter year, meaning irrigation on farms is improved and water constraints are eased, resulting in boosted crop yields and more planting, which all require more labour on farms. The primary study specification focuses on the contemporaneous change in farmer prices to preserve statistical power. Adding a one-year lag cuts the sample by approximately 6%, in the already restricted ten-country 26-year panel. In this small country, a large year fixed effects context, the precision gained by retaining every observation, I believe, outweighs the insight provided by the lag. Accordingly, I maintain the static model as the baseline estimate and report the lagged version as a robustness check on dynamic adjustment. Longer distributed lag structures would exacerbate the observation size problem and are left for future work when longer, more complete datasets are utilised.

6. Conclusion

6.1 Study Summary

This study set out to answer whether coffee price movements translate into jobs for agricultural workers across ten prominent Latin American coffee exporters between 1997 and 2022. The fully specified baseline model does not find statistical significance between the variables of interest, although in the dynamic one-year farmer price lag model, the contemporaneous response becomes 0.0106pp and is highly statistically significant at the 1% level. The lagged term itself remains insignificant, implying a quick within-harvest adjustment rather than a drawn-out hiring cycle. An exhaustive control variable set guided by the literature and Driscoll-Kraay standard errors makes the model statistically robust.

H₁ predicted a positive relationship between coffee prices and agricultural employment; the baseline result is null, yet the dynamic robustness check offers support, suggesting that farmers do respond but largely within the current agricultural year. H₂ suggested asymmetry between positive and negative coffee price shocks; neither of the coefficients was statistically significant. A Wald's test failed to reject their equality, thus, the secondary hypothesis has no support, in contrast to the findings of Ghoshray & Mohan (2021).

To my knowledge, this is the first panel estimate of producer-price responses for agricultural employment in Latin America after the 1989 dissolution of the International Coffee Agreement. By synergising an evidence-based control

set and rigorous error structure, this study complements micro work from Vietnam and Tanzania and updates dated simulation exercises for Brazil, as seen in the literature review. The insignificant asymmetry result nuances narratives that state smallholders absorb the downside of commodity cycles more acutely than the upside.

6.2 Policy Implications

The dynamic lagged model shows that when both current and lagged real-farm age prices are included, the contemporaneous measure is 0.0106pp, while the year lag price measure is insignificant. Farmers, therefore, adjust labour demand within the same agricultural year rather than spreading recruitment across seasons, therefore, any policy after the harvest will miss the narrow hiring window. Given this, policymakers could implement measures such as contingent cash transfers that automatically trigger when coffee price futures cross a specified threshold. This would give smallholder farms the liquidity to ensure workers and inputs are purchased accordingly, before the main harvest. Information is also important, policymakers should ensure farmers are educated on crop futures and price signals are sent via SMS or apps to ensure farmers internalise global market signals swiftly, to ensure efficient labour allocation.

Furthermore, given insignificance in the baseline model and a modest employment response of 0.0106pp in the lagged model, policymakers should focus labour policies on productivity, instead of worker retention. As highlighted by Harvey et al (2021), farms in Latin America are becoming mechanised, decoupling employment from price changes. Upskilling policies, particularly in poorer rural areas, should ensure that growth in agriculture is more equitable and amplified. Evidence from Uganda (Bussolo et al. 2007) reinforces the significance of coffee farm growth; coffee price booms resulted in multiplier effects surrounding coffee-dependent regions, overall boosting economic growth.

6.3 Limitations

Several limitations can temper the quality of the results. A key limitation of the study is that annual frequency is used, yet the results show that almost the entire adjustment from price shocks is completed within the same harvest year. This can imply that the 12-month aggregated study could be concealing short-lived hiring cycles, and overall underestimate the significance of coffee prices for agricultural employment. Case-wise deletion results in the study having 226 observations instead of 260, and 212 in the lagged specification, which widens standard errors. Using quarterly or monthly labour force or social security registers can exploit within-year, not cross-year variation, and higher frequency datasets would expand the number of datapoints, overall improving statistical power. This would also allow researchers to experiment with longer distributed lag models, which were out of scope for this study due to data constraints. In addition, measurement error hinders statistical significance: national labour surveys of the countries in the

sample differ in whether they count informal workers, and several countries replace true farm gate prices with wholesale proxies, muting price signals. Using larger, better-defined micro datasets would allow a study to have richer and statistically more robust results.

6.4 Direction for Future Research

There was a plan to investigate child-labour responses as an additional hypothesis, but it was restricted due to data limitations. The intuition behind this hypothesis was the study by Beck et al (2018), who found a substitution effect between adult and child workers on coffee farms in Vietnam depending on how coffee prices change. This study would allow policymakers to gain critical insights that could help ensure that measures are in place to minimise child labour and protect school attendance, preventing future workforce deskilling.

Utilising richer datasets, like the International Coffee Organisation database, can allow researchers to expand this research to different regions and experiment with changes in prices of different coffee varieties, such as Southeast Asia, where countries, such as Vietnam, predominantly produce Robusta Coffee. This will allow us to see if a muted agriculture employment response is unique to Arabica-coffee-producing Latin America or is a feature of different coffee economies across the globe.

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